

1 **Xist mediates resistance in HER2+ breast cancer.**

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7 We demonstrate here by studying HER2+ breast cancers in humans in vivo using whole transcriptome
8 technologies that the non-coding RNA that functions in developmental imprinting in females, Xist is a
9 relevant entity in resistance to the monoclonal antibody used for the treatment of HER2+ breast cancer,
10 trastuzumab. The expression of Xist was among those whose quantity was most different when comparing
11 the tumors of those with pathologic complete response (pCR) and those with partial response (PR), which
12 we interpret as resistance. Thus, Xist is activated and silenced by loss of tumor suppressor functions
13 (including Rb1 and p53), by activity in the DNA damage and repair signaling pathways, both homologous
14 recombination- and non homologous end joining-based, and has functions in multiple aspects of the tumor
15 life cycle, including subtype selection, metastasis and resistance.
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Results

We measured total transcription using next-generation sequencing technologies in a cell culture model of resistance to trastuzumab and in HER2+ breast cancer *in vivo*, in the tumors of patients with treatment failure (residual disease) or complete response to the HER2-targeted treatment trastuzumab to discover transcriptional changes associated with resistance to trastuzumab in humans with HER2+ breast cancer.

Figure 1: Engineered trastuzumab resistance in HER2+ breast cancer cells *in vitro* results in induction of the non-coding RNA Xist.

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n=2 wild-type BT474 cells

n=8 4 separate *in vitro* generated trastuzumab resistance clones (BT474) n=2 each

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
235446_at	6.56E-02	-2.02	-4.401006	-2.35E-01	XIST	7676/54675	86.0

We next measured Xist induction or repression *in vivo* in humans with HER2+ breast cancer by quantifying total transcription in bulk tumors *in vivo* rather than breast cancer, in patients with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab, comparing based on clinical outcome: pathologic complete response (pCR) or residual disease (RD), which we interpreted as treatment failure.

Figure 2: Xist induction is among the most significant changes in gene expression transcriptome-wide when comparing the tumors of patients with HER2+ breast cancer based on clinical outcome:

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n=2 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab (pCR)

n=2 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab with residual disease (RD)

Probe ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
221728_x_at	0.02403709	-2.7106727	-3.35923	-1.2349	XIST	2114/22283	90.5

Discussion

We described here the induction of Xist *in vitro* and *in vivo* in HER2+ breast cancer. In an accompanying manuscript, we describe induction and silencing of Xist non-coding RNA resulting from *in vitro* exposure to agents used for the treatment of triple negative breast cancer and luminal-type hormone receptor positive breast cancers. Xist is a biologically important entity when considering the relevant actors in disease resistance in human breast cancer of any subtype. Xist likely functions as an epigenetic switch, controlling the activation and repression of a wide array of genes through the polycomb repressive complex (PRC2) which ultimately governs tumor evolution at the clonal level; Xist is described to interact with EZH2 at H3K27me3 targets (1).

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Methods

We utilized whole transcriptome methodologies with R-based computational quantitative methods in conjunction with RNA-sequencing and/or microarray-based technology (public or published) to measure total transcription in breast cancer cells engineered to developed resistance to trastuzumab or in the primary tumors of humans with HER2+ breast cancer following treatment with trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for this study of Xist transcriptional dynamics in HER2+ breast cancer.

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References

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